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‘HIGH- PERFORMANCE WORK PRACTICES’ AND EMPLOYEES’ CREATIVITY: TESTING THE RELATIONSHIP

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Abstract

Objective- *Today business environments have changed dramatically from the past and to cope effectively with ‘cut throat competition’, it was recognized that ‘human resource’ and its alignment with business strategies is the only way to increase organizational effectiveness and competitiveness. As a survival strategy “High Performance Work System” (HPWS) has emerged as one of the most popular organization development strategies or interventions of organizations to maximize firms’ competitive advantages. The large number of companies, in particular in IT industry, is inclined towards designing and implementing High Performance Work Practices (HPWPs) in order to improve organizational performance and productivity. HPWPs may be introduced individually or in groups, called ‘bundles’ of practices, to ensure improved performance of individual employees and of the organizations employing them. At the same time, increasingly turbulent environments, heightened competition, and unpredictable technological changes have brought to the forefront of management cognition the recognition, development and sustenance of employee creativity. Thus, the objective of the paper is to provide an insight to the managers for developing and implementing the most effective HPWPs which complement and strengthen the empowerment of employees and in turn enhance creative and productive performance. Secondary objective is to analyze the impact of HPWPs on creativity of the employees by developing a link between these practices and employee creativity.*

Design / Methodology/ Approach- *The present research paper is an empirical study and is based on primary data. The sample of this study was 120 Indian IT employees. The data was collected by administering the questionnaire. Pearson correlation and Hierarchical regression method were employed for analysis.*

Findings- *The results of the study suggest that the implementation of HPWPs in IT companies have a strong positive link with creativity of employees. The result showed Empowerment has largest influence on*

employees' creativity. Also, the correlation of HPWPs and creativity is found to be very significant. This research study analyzed the strength of impact of Empowerment on employees' creativity vis-à-vis other HPWPs i.e., information sharing, training and skill development and flexible job designs.

Limitations- Present research is conducted on a very small sample and taken from IT sector only. This limits the generalization of the findings to large populations. Thus, further studies need to be conducted in different types of organizations.

Practical implications- This paper can inspire managers and experts of their fields for bringing certain changes in the way of execution of existing/modern HR practices. Employees are an integral part of organizations. Thus by empowering the employees, organizations can achieve results and can retain creative employees for long.

Originality/Value- The previous works have focused at the firm level performance and financial outcomes. Also, the impact of HPWPs on employee creativity has received scant attention from both academics and practitioners. Thus, this study is an attempt to fill the void.

Keywords: High-Performance Work Practices; Employee Creativity; Empowerment; Information sharing; Training and skill development.

Introduction

Organizations today are remarkably different from the past. The global competition, work-force diversity, organizational restructuring, the best quality service revolution and innovative technologies have forced organizations to think about their approach to compete in this fast paced environment. During the last few years, to survive, a large number of companies are inclined towards designing and implementing high performance work practices (HPWPs) in order to improve organizational performance and productivity. These practices denote a strategic approach to human resource management and its utilization in the organization, in order to develop a highly skilled, flexible, motivated and creative work force. HPWPs are intended to better use the employee skills and knowledge to facilitate the organizations to become cost efficient, flexible, and more responsive to changing markets and technologies. Thus, the need to create a more skilled workforce for employment in high performance work organizations producing high quality & high value products and services has become an

important priority for policy-makers in industries. Increasingly turbulent environments, heightened competition, and unpredictable technological changes have brought to the forefront of management cognition the recognition, development and sustenance of employee creativity. To survive in this turbulent environment, organizations have to be creative and responsive to the changing environment (Roberts & Amit, 2003). Creativity is defined as the production of novel and useful ideas by an individual or by a group of individuals working together (Amabile, 1983) and has been found to fundamentally contribute to organizational innovation, effectiveness, and survival (Amabile, 1996). According to researchers, this creativity cannot be instituted without the involvement of employees. Also, the resource-based theories of competitive advantage focus on the role employees play in developing and maintaining a firm's competitive capabilities and lay stress on keeping the workforce rightly and appropriately encouraged and motivated. The organizational researchers found that creative performance of employees is necessary for achieving competitive edge over competitors (Shalley, 1995). Creative employees provide important raw material in shape of novel and useful ideas which bring further development and improvement in the organization (Woodman, Sawyer & Griffin, 1993). As a result, organizations can respond to opportunities in a better way to grow and compete dynamically (Kanter, 1983). Organizations set the tone of social exchange relationships by providing employees with a multitude of resources such as appreciation, prestige, growth, recognition, fairness, and empowerment through their HRM practices. In return, employees may expand their definitions of job responsibilities and be motivated to engage in more creative behaviors. Surprisingly, the review of literature suggests that the impact of Human Resource Management (HRM) practices on employee creativity has received scant attention from both academics and practitioners.

Thus, the purpose of the present study was to examine the effect of HPWPs on employees' creativity. This research contributes to the HRM literature by examining the individual perceptions of innovative modern HR practices and its role on employees' creativity. This approach expands view of organizational performance from mere financial impact to employee-level factor, thus bridging the perspectives of SHRM (Strategic human resource management).

Objective of the study

SHRM comprises a system of innovative HR practices that produce the employees' competencies and behaviours the company needs to achieve its strategic goals (Dessler & Varkkey, 2009). Thus, SHRM is implementation of innovative HR practices to develop potential human capital and to increase their involvement in work process. Also, the social exchange theory (SET) provides theoretical foundation of creative behavior of employees. According to SET when employees are given values by empowerment and training, the employees feel sense of consideration and they repay the organization by showing engaged behavior. This engaged behavior of employees motivates them to perform more than their duties and results into creativity and innovation in the organization (Saks, 2006). Although, like social exchange theory, some researchers have provided theoretical frameworks of employee creativity; however, empirical evidence is limited (Afshari et al, 2011). Moreover, there is limited empirical evidence about the factors which lead towards creativity of employees (Jansen et al, 2006). Thus, the objective of the paper is to find out the factors in terms of HR practices which lead towards employees' creativity.

Thus, the objectives of the present study:

1. To provide an insight towards the most effective HPWPs (from selected practices) which complement and strengthen the empowerment of employees and in turn enhance creative performance
2. To analyze relationship between the HPWPs and the creativity of the employees.

Literature review

Research in the field of SHRM has been guided by various approaches. The first of these approaches was Walton's (1985) *High-Commitment Management*. Walton based his HRM model on employee commitment and called for the combined usage of certain personnel practices, such as job redesign, job flexibility, problem-solving groups, team-based working and minimal status differences in order to keep the workforce sufficiently committed. The next approach that became popular was Lawler's (1986) *High-Involvement Management*. High-Involvement management was considered to be the less restrictive interpretation of high-commitment management (Wood, 1999) and focused on four principles – Power, Information,

Knowledge and Rewards – for building an involved workforce. The most recent approach is called as *High- Performance Management* (Huselid, 1995; Appelbaum, Bailey, Berg, & Kalleberg, 2000).

High performance organizations ensure that their employees are equipped to make devolved decision, have the necessary information, skills and incentives, and are responsible for decisions essential for innovation, improvement and rapid response to change. This system of HR management practices is focused to motivate employees by adopting best HR practices such as employment security, job design, training and skill development (Delery and Doty, 1996), selectivity in recruiting, comparatively high wages (Snell and Dean, 1992), incentive pay based on performance appraisal (Wright et al, 2003), employee ownership (Huselid and Becker, 1995), information sharing (Guthrie et al, 2009), participation and empowerment (Delery and Doty, 1996; Godard, 2001), self-managed teams (Guthrie et al, 2009), reduced status distinctions and barriers (Macky and Boxell, 2007), and measurement of the HR practices through regular employee surveys (Huselid and Becker, 2000).

Employee Creativity: Solving problems creatively requires extensive and effortful cognitive processing (Reiter-Palmon & Illies, 2004). Although creativity literature makes explicit acknowledgment of creative behaviors (e.g. problem or task presentation, preparation, response generation) much of the research relating to creativity has concentrated on contextual factors that influence creative performance and the creative behavior aspect has not received attention commensurate with its importance. Only when such a connection is explored empirically, will give more precise understanding of creativity and shall help management in identifying individual, group and organizational practices that can actually aid in enhancing the competitive advantage of organizations.

The argument behind *high-performance management* is that competitive markets now demand that ‘firms emphasize quality and are able to adapt rapidly to changing conditions’, which in turn means that they ‘must increasingly rely upon the creativity, ingenuity and problem-solving ability of their workers’ (Wood & Wall 2007, p. 1339).

Given below is a brief description of the high performance work practices that have been identified for the present study.

High performance work practices: After extensive review of literature and discussions with HR experts and employees of IT companies, the high performance work practices that influence employee abilities, motivation and opportunity to participate were selected because these are the factors responsible for employee creative and innovative performance. The literature on HPWPs identifies a set of HRM practices that have been found to significantly impact employee performance. Next, the study develops probable relationship between HPWPs and employee creativity. Practices pertaining to selection, training, performance appraisal and career planning relate to the ability and skill development of employees. Practices of organizations on pay for performance, job security, work-life balance, and information sharing were considered to be part of motivation. Opportunity to participate was emphasized by the HR practices on Participation in decision making, teamwork and autonomy. Thus, High-performance work practices can enhance the positive exchange between the employee and employer, thereby enhancing employee creativity and innovative behaviors.

Selective staffing can be used to try and select employees who are more likely to be creative or who have higher innate creative ability (Guest, 1997; Shalley & Gilson, 2004). Selection is one of the major tools for developing and promoting corporate culture (Schein, 2004) and can ensure that the candidates are carefully screened to “fit in” to the existing corporate culture (Nazir, 2005). Organizations can focus on screening prior to selection to try to hire employees based on their task expertise and cognitive skills needed for creativity.

Empowerment forms the core of a high-performance work system is an organization that enables non-managerial employees to participate in substantive decisions. Empowerment, as a HRM practice, has found strong support in the literature and has been included in the set of high performance practices by various researchers in western context (Godard, 2001). Empowerment and participatory systems enable employees to understand the firm’s competitive position and enable them to work towards improving their firm’s position (Wright et al., 2003). Among the various HR practices, employee empowerment and training are most popular. The employee empowerment concept is grounded on the assumption that employees are the unexploited source of knowledge, initiative and creativity [34].

The study of Cakar and Erturk on SMEs found that employee empowerment is positively related with creativity and innovation in the SMEs. Similarly, concepts related to empowerment such as high job autonomy, freedom in deciding what to do, decentralization and sense of control over ones work lead towards creativity among employees [38].

Information sharing enables the sharing of information on financial, performance and operational strategies (Pfeffer & Veiga, 1999), which influences employee perceptions about role structures (Guest, 1997) and enables them to participate better (Wright et al., 2003). A good communication system provides employees with data that is timely and relevant to their particular work process, thereby influencing them personally to either expend or withhold effort (Konrad, 2006). Researchers have argued that information-sharing can lead to internalization of firm's goals and values by employees, can enhance feelings of mutual trust, and can make employees feel important to the company (Bartel, 2004).

Training & Skill development can be used to provide educational opportunities that can enhance task domain expertise. The employees should acquire technical skills, interpersonal skills and solid knowledge through training to perform their jobs efficiently and effectively (Eldridge & Nisar, 2006). The lack of ongoing training programs leads to lower performance of employees. This relationship is also supported by Combs et al., (2006) who found that abilities, skills and knowledge of employees are enhanced through HR practices such as training and empowerment which result into creativity of the employees. Research on training for creative problem solving has indicated that training can help enhance employees' level of creativity (e.g., Basudur, Wakabayashi, & Graen, 1990).

Theoretical literature suggests the positive relationship between training and creativity (Ambile, 1988; Gervais et al., 2012). But studies suggest that the empirical evidence of this relationship is lacking. Critical examination of numerous recent studies reveals the association between employee's personal characteristics and employee creativity (Chen et al., 2011), however, little of this research focused on human resource practices i.e. training and empowerment, which predicts employee creativity (Jiang et al., 2012; Thompson & Heron, 2006).

Performance based pay or effective performance-based appraisal can help in identifying the training needs and thus aid in improving the creativity relevant skills. The practice of *performance-based pay* can be effective motivators of employee performance. Literature has found strong support for the relationship between both these practices and employee performance (Agarwal & Ferratt, 1999; Appelbaum et al., 2000; Guthrie, 2001; Huselid, 1995; Ichniowski & Shaw, 1999; Paul & Anantharaman, 2003). Merit-based promotion and performance oriented appraisal signal an organization's intent to establish a long-term exchange relationship with its employees (Sun, Aryee, & Law, 2007).

Flexible job design and team-based working can lead to work enrichment and an opportunity to learn from other team members thereby contributing to better creativity relevant skills. With the business environment becoming more dynamic and unpredictable, team-based work and flexible job designs have become need of the hour. Flexible job designs can lead to work enrichment so that employees have high levels of discretion and decision-making powers by enhancing autonomy and formation of teams that have considerable autonomy (Wood & Wall, 2007). Flexible job designs improve knowledge of employees and allow them to see the company from number of perspectives (Farh, Podsakoff, & Organ, 1990). This enhanced exposure to the working of the organization can significantly enhance their domain-relevant skills that are essential for creativity.

Thus, the hypothesis of the present study is:

High-Performance Work Practices (such as selective hiring, empowerment, information sharing, performance-based-pay, training & skill development, and flexible job designs) would be positively correlated with employees' creativity.

Research Methodology: Participants:

The current study included around 120 software employees from Indian IT industry. The companies were located in the north regions of the country including New Delhi, Noida and Gurgaon. Some of the companies were Genpact, Cognizant, TCS, etc. Primary data were collected through administered questionnaires to assess the relationship between high performance work practices and employees' creativity. The respondents were approached personally for their responses and interviews. Two scales, along with personal data sheet, were

administered to the participants individually. After data collection, the responses were scored for each score and appropriate statistical tools were used to analyze it.

Measures:

High-Performance Work Practices: High performance work practices by Huselid, 1995; Huselid & Becker, 1995; Delery & Doty, 1996; Becker & Huselid, 2000; Hartog & Verburg, 2004; Snell and Dean, 1992; US Department of Labor, 1993. For HPWPs, 6 practices were included and were measured on the scale of 23-items ($\alpha = .86$). Respondents were asked to identify the extent to which these selected HPWPs were implemented in their organizations.

Employee creativity: George and Zhou (2001) developed a 13-item scale ($\alpha = .96$) to measure creativity and Employee creativity. George and Zhou (2001) developed a 13-item scale (adopting three items from Scott and Bruce (1994).

Analysis

The obtained data was analyzed by using correlation and regression method in order to examine the effect of six HPWPs on employees' creativity.

Table 1: Correlation Index of Variables (N= 120; two tailed test)

Predictors	SH	Empowerment	IS	PBP	TSD	FJD	Creativity
SH	1	.409 000	-.057 .537	.041 .055	.123 .181	.122 .092	.284 .001
Empowerment		1	.742 .000	.252 .006	.302 .001	.432 .001	.766 .000
IS			1	.419 .000	.517 .001	.296 .001	.333 .001
PBP				1	.158 .080	.565 .000	-.122 .092
TSD					1	.122 .092	.432 .001
FJD						1	.517 .000
Creativity							1

Note: SH: selective hiring; IS: information sharing; PBP: performance based pay; TSD: training & skill development; FJD: flexible job design

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Results of correlation analysis (Table-1) indicate that six HR practices (SH, empowerment, IS, PBP, TSD and FSD) are significantly correlated with employees' creativity of IT personnel. Five practices were found positively correlated with employees' creativity except one (performance based pay). The positive correlation observed between selective hiring practice and employees' creativity is low (.284).

Table 2: Hierarchical Regression Analysis for Employees' Creativity

Variables	β	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	F
<i>Step-1</i>		.901	.811	.796	59.57***
Age	-.256**				
Gender	-0.49				
Education	.088*				
Job-ten	.234***				
Org-ten	.583				
Salary	-1.282***				
<i>Step-2</i>		.971	.942	.935	115.447***
SH	.999				
Empowerment	.698***				
IS	.169*				
PBP	-.390***				
TSD	.228***				
FJD	.246***				

* $p < .05$; ** $p < .01$; *** $p < .001$

Next, hierarchical regression analysis (Table-2) was performed to test the hypothesis. Result indicates that demographic variables accounted for 81% variance in the prediction of creativity ($R^2 = .811$; $F = 59.57$, $p < .001$). Beta values of each demographic variables revealed that age ($\beta = -.256$, $p = .01$), education ($\beta = .088$, $p < .05$), job tenure ($\beta = -.234$, $p < .001$) and salary ($\beta = -1.282$, $p < .001$), are more significant predictors of creativity of employees'.

The results of regression analysis further suggest that HR practices have made significant contribution in the prediction of employees' creativity ($R^2 = .942$, $F = 115.44$, $p < .001$). The beta values revealed that HR practice of performance based pay ($\beta = -.390$, $p < .001$) significantly negatively predicted employees' creativity. Whereas, four practices such as empowerment ($\beta =$

.698, $p < .001$), information sharing ($\beta = .169$, $p < .05$), training & skill development ($\beta = .228$, $p < .001$) and flexible job design ($\beta = .246$, $p < .001$) predicted employees' creativity positively.

Conclusion

The main objective of the study was to examine the relationship between six HPWPs and employees' creativity in employees working in IT firms. Correlation and regression results partially supported the hypothesized relationship that was six HPWPs would positively predict the employees' creativity. This study suggested that six HR practices such as; selective hiring, empowerment, information sharing, performance-based pay, training & skill development and flexible job design have different and independent effects on employees' creativity.

The present study contributes practically by concluding that practices like empowerment, training & skill development and flexible job designs definitely provides a strong base for dynamically changing organizations to manage the creative culture that can promote their competencies as well as other strategic priorities to gain competitive advantage. This study also found that when employees are given time to time training and required empowerment, they feel that the organization is more concerned about them and in turn it enhances the positive exchange between the employee and organization, thereby enhancing employee creativity and productive performance. More specifically, employees exhibit the highest creativity when they work on flexible jobs/ job rotations and were supervised in a supportive manner. This paper can inspire managers and experts of their fields for bringing certain changes in the way of execution of existing/modern HR practices. As employees are an integral part of organizations, HRD professionals should support employee creativity not only at organizational level but also at individual level by delivering relevant HPWPs.

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